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Effects of Physics Education Technology (PhET) Simulations On Students' Motivation and Achievement in Electricity Concepts in Colleges of Education in North-Central, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

This study investigated the Effects of Physics Education Technology (PhET) Simulations on Students' Motivation and Achievement in Electricity Concepts in Colleges of Education in North-Central, Nigeria. Four research questions and hypotheses guided the study. The research design employed was quasi-experimental design of pre-test, post-test non-equivalent groups design. The population of the study was made up of 143 NCE 1 students. Multi-stage sampling technique was used to select 70 NCE 1 students comprising both experimental (35) and control (35) groups. The research instruments used for data collection were Electricity Achievement Test (EAT) and Electricity Motivation Questionnaire (EMQ). The instruments were validated and subjected to reliability test and coefficients of 0.80 and 0.85 were obtained for EAT and EMQ using Kuder-Richardson formula 21 (K-R21) and Cronbach's Alpha respectively. Data collected were analyzed using mean rank for research questions one and three and frequency counts, mean and standard deviation for research questions two and four. Mann-Whitney U test was used to test hypotheses one and three, while ANCOVA was used to test hypotheses two and four at 0.05 level of significance. Based on the findings, it was recommended among others that PhET simulations be incorporated into the teaching of Electricity concepts to improve students' motivation and achievement. The findings also support the continued use of PhET for both male and female students, as it enhances learning outcomes for all learners with only slight gender differences.

Keywords: PhET Simulations, Students' Motivation, Achievement, Electricity Concepts, Colleges of Education

1. INTRODUCTION

Simulation is the process of using computer programmes to create a model that mimics the behavior of a real-world system. They are powerful tools used across various disciplines to model, analyze and predict complex systems. They involve creating digital representations of real-world systems and running simulations to observe how the system behaves under different conditions (Mahdi, Laafou & Mohamed, 2018). The integration of computers in teaching physics at the university level began in the mid-20th century, when computers became more readily available for academic and research use (Mahdi, Laafou & Mohamed, 2018). The process of incorporating simulations into education can be traced back to the growing need for more interactive and engaging teaching methods, particularly in fields like electricity, where hands-on experience and visualization of abstract concepts are crucial (Droui & Hajjami, 2014).

PhET interactive simulations provides an alternative approach to the traditional laboratory and can enhance students learning through visualization, demonstrations and illustrations (Makransky,

Terkildsen & Mayer, 2017). The primary goal of PhET simulations is to make abstract scientific concepts more accessible and engaging to learners of all ages and backgrounds. By providing interactive visualizations and allowing users to manipulate variables in real-time, PhET simulations help students develop a deeper understanding of fundamental principles in physics and other scientific disciplines. These simulations have been widely adopted in tertiary-level physics education to facilitate active learning and conceptual understanding. Furthermore, PhET simulations are research-based, highly interactive, animated and easy to use. They create a game-like environment, can be used to model real-life scenarios and do not need many computer specifications (University of Colorado, 2024). Educational technology, including simulations like PhET, is increasingly used to enhance the learning experience in physics. It covers a wide range of topics including Electricity, Optics, Mechanics, heat etc. It has a circuit construction kit. These tools offer interactive and visual representations of complex concepts, which may impact various aspects of student learning Electricity concepts. Electricity is a fundamental aspect in physics that involves abstract concepts which can be challenging for students to grasp. Understanding its principles is crucial for success in both physics and related fields.

Motivation becomes one of the most important factors in learning (Davoudi & Parpaouchi, 2016). If students are motivated to learn, it will affect learning outcomes, because their understanding of concepts will be better (Khairunnisak, 2018). The more students are motivated, the better their understanding of concepts (Sihombing et al., 2021). Motivation serves as the basis for gaining understanding of scientific concepts due to its significance in improving students' concept formation (Albalate et. al., 2018). According to Albalate et. al., (2018), without motivation, students' learning will be basically by rote memorization which will in turn lead to inadequate understanding of scientific concepts.

Achievement in Electricity concepts is the measurable outcome of learning, typically assessed through tests, conceptual inventories or practical problem-solving tasks. High achievement indicates not just recall but deep conceptual understanding and the ability to apply principles in novel situations. Studies have demonstrated that using PhET interactive simulations significantly improves students' achievement in physics topics, including electrodynamics and electrostatics (Najib, Md-Ali, & Yaacob, 2022; Uwambajimana & Minani, 2023). The field of academic achievement is very wide-ranging and covers a broad variety of educational outcomes, the definition of academic achievement depends on the indicators used to measure it and gender may be one of such indicators.

Gender disparities in education, especially in Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics (STEM), remain a global concern. Girls and women are underrepresented in these fields due to systemic biases, stereotype threats and lack of role models (Wang & Degol, 2017; UNESCO, 2023). Recent studies indicate that, gender bias in teacher expectations and classroom interactions can discourage girls from engaging in physics and mathematics (Francis et al., 2022). Physics education has historically been challenged by gender disparities in both interest and achievement levels. Girls and women are often underrepresented in physics classrooms and careers globally (UNESCO, 2021). Electricity, as a core topic in secondary and introductory university physics, involves concepts that can be abstract and mathematically demanding. Simulations like Circuit Construction Kit allow students to visualize electric flow, understand circuit behavior and connect mathematical formulas to real-world actions (PhET Interactive Simulations, 2023). Teachers can use simulations to gauge understanding through tasks and explorations, thereby providing individualized support to both male and female learners. When used alongside gender-sensitive instructional strategies (e.g., equitable participation, countering bias), simulations can help ensure that both boys and girls achieve mastery in electricity concepts.

Physics is challenging to study because students tend to view some of the laws and concepts as abstract (Guido, 2018). This may have resulted to the decline in the percentage of Colleges of Education students choosing physics as their core course due to their level of exposure at the secondary school level. Reports from National Commission for Colleges of Education (2023), on students' enrollment, show that there is a decrease in the number of students enrolling in Physics Education in Colleges of Education in Nigeria due to lack of interest in physics and poor performance of students in physics at their secondary school stage. This poses a great task to educators in physics to reinvent the wheel of teaching by developing exciting and meaningful ways to facilitate learning.

When used efficiently, simulation-based learning strategies can overcome the problems of motivation and academic achievement in physics.

While traditional teaching methods (lectures, textbooks, static diagrams) are common in Colleges of Education, these methods may not adequately support students' conceptual understanding of Electricity concepts. Abstract notions such as voltage, resistance and charge are difficult to visualize in conventional classrooms. This gap contributes to persistent low motivation and substandard academic outcomes among student-teachers. Nigeria's educational system suffers from a lack of resources at all stages of education (UNICEF Nigeria, 2015). In spite of this, teachers continue to use the conventional method to teach students, concentrating on their cognitive dimension. Studies have shown that the bulky nature of the curriculum makes teachers employ the conventional method (Amponsah, 2020; Amponsah, Boateng & Mohammed; Amponsah & Ochonogor, 2016a & b) to enable them finish the syllabus on time instead of innovative strategies like the use of Simulations in teaching and learning physics. Thus, integrating PhET interactive simulations in physics classes may be one of the remedies for correcting poor academic achievement and lack of motivation towards physics, particularly electricity concepts by students of Colleges of Education in the North Central part of Nigeria. Specifically, the objectives of the study were to:

- i. find out the difference between the mean motivation scores of students taught Electricity concepts in physics using PhET simulations and those taught using conventional teaching method.
- ii. find out the difference between the mean achievement scores of students taught Electricity concepts in physics using PhET simulations and those taught using conventional teaching method.
- iii. find out the difference between the mean motivation scores of male and female students taught Electricity concepts in physics using PhET simulations and those taught using conventional teaching method.
- iv. find out the difference between the mean achievement scores of male and female students taught Electricity concepts in physics using PhET simulations and those taught using conventional teaching method.

Research Questions

The following research questions were raised to guide the conduct of this study:

1. What is the difference between the mean motivation scores of students taught Electricity concepts in physics using PhET Simulations and those taught using Conventional teaching method?
2. What is the difference between the mean Achievement scores of students taught Electricity concepts in physics using PhET Simulations and those taught using Conventional teaching method?
3. What is the difference between the mean Motivation scores of male and female students taught Electricity concepts in physics using PhET Simulations and those taught using Conventional teaching method?
4. What is the difference between the mean Achievement scores of male and female students taught Electricity concepts in physics using PhET Simulations and those taught using Conventional teaching method?

Hypotheses

H₀₁ There is no significant difference between the mean Motivation scores of students taught Electricity concepts in physics using PhET Simulations and those taught using conventional teaching method.

H₀₂ There is no significant difference between the mean Achievement scores of students taught Electricity concepts in physics using PhET Simulations and those taught using conventional teaching method.

H₀₃ There is no significant difference between the mean Motivation scores of male and female students taught Electricity concepts in physics using PhET Simulations and those taught using conventional teaching method.

H₀₄ There is no significant difference between the mean Achievement scores of male and female students taught Electricity concepts in physics using PhET Simulations and those taught using conventional teaching method.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

This study employed quasi-experimental design. Specifically, the study applied the pre-test, post-test non-equivalent control groups design. The population of this study comprised one hundred and forty-three (143) NCE 1 students studying physics in public Colleges of Education in North-Central, Nigeria. A sample size of 70 students were drawn through multi-stage sampling technique. At the first stage of sampling, simple random sampling technique was used to select three states located at the North-Central part of Nigeria. At the second stage of sampling, random sampling technique was used to select four public Colleges of Education from the population. At stage three of sampling, to obtain a more robust and representative sample and to ensure that the sample reflects variations across multiple schools rather than relying on a single institution per group, the researcher selected four Colleges of Education, assigning two institutions to the experimental group and two to the control group. There were 35 students in experimental group and 35 in control group. The instruments used for data collection were Electricity Achievement Test (EAT) and Electricity Motivation Questionnaire (EMQ). The instruments were validated by three physics lecturers in Colleges of Education within the study area. The test items were constructed in line with the learning objectives and cognitive levels as specified in the table of specification. A pilot test was conducted using one intact class of thirty (20) physics students in a College of Education that was not part of the sampled Institutions selected for this study. The reliability of EAT and EMQ were determined using Kuder-Richardson formula 21 (K-R21) and Cronbach Alpha respectively. Lesson plans were prepared separately for both experimental and control groups. Those in experimental group were taught Electricity concepts using Physics Education Technology (PhET) Simulations while those in control group were taught using conventional method of teaching. Data collected were analyzed using mean rank for research questions one and three and frequency counts, mean and standard deviation for research questions two and four. Mann-Whitney U test was used to test hypotheses one and three, while ANCOVA was used to test hypotheses two and four at 0.05 level of significance.

3. RESULTS

Research Question 1: *What is the difference between the mean motivation scores of students taught Electricity concepts in physics using PhET Simulations and those taught using Conventional teaching method?*

Table 1: Mean Rank Motivation Scores of Students in Experimental and Control Group

Groups	N	Mean Rank	Mean Difference	Sum of Ranks
Experimental	35	23.38	6.63	276.00
Control	35	16.75		195.00
Total	70			

Table 1 shows mean rank motivation scores of students in both experimental and control group. The mean rank scores of students taught Electricity concepts using PhET is 23.38 and sum of ranks is 276.00 while those taught Electricity concepts using conventional method of teaching is 16.75 and sum of ranks is 195.00. The difference in the mean rank is 6.63 in favour of experimental group. The result implies that students in experimental group had higher mean motivation score than those in control group.

Research Question 2: *What is the difference between the mean Achievement scores of students taught Electricity concepts in physics using PhET Simulations and those taught using Conventional teaching method?*

Table 2: Mean Achievement Scores of Students in Experimental and Control Group

Groups	N	Pre-test		Post-test		Mean gain
		\bar{x}	SD	\bar{x}	SD	
Experimental	35	11.54	3.457	17.83	2.953	6.29
Control	35	10.61	2.611	11.76	2.538	1.15

Table 2 shows that the experimental group has a pre-test mean score of 11.54, a post-test mean score of 17.83 and mean gain of 6.29 while the control group has a pre-test mean score of 10.61, a post-test mean score of 11.76 and mean gain of 1.15. The experimental group has a higher mean gain than control group as the difference in mean gain is 5.14. This shows that the experimental group taught

Electricity concepts using PhET Simulations have higher achievement score than those taught with conventional teaching method.

Research Question 3: *What is the difference between the mean Motivation scores of male and female students taught Electricity concepts in physics using PhET Simulations and those taught using Conventional teaching method?*

Table 3: Mean Rank Motivation Scores of Male and Female Students in Experimental Group

Groups	N	Mean Rank	Mean Difference	Sum of Ranks
Male	27	18.73	0.15	189.00
Female	8	18.58		188.00
Total	35			

Table 3 shows mean rank motivation scores of students in experimental group. The mean rank scores of male students are 18.73 and sum of ranks is 189.00 while that of their female counterparts is 18.58 and sum of ranks is 188.00. The slight difference in the mean rank is 0.15 in favour of the male students.

Research Question 4: *What is the difference between the mean Achievement scores of male and female students taught Electricity concepts in physics using PhET Simulations and those taught using Conventional teaching method?*

Table 4: Mean Achievement Scores of Male and Female Students in Experimental Group

Variables	N	Pre-test		Post-test		Mean gain
		\bar{x}	SD	\bar{x}	SD	
Male	27	10.46	2.739	14.84	1.759	4.38
Female	8	9.69	1.584	13.61	2.438	3.92

In table 4, the mean achievement scores of male students taught Electricity concepts using PhET Simulations is 10.46 and 14.84 for the pre-test and post-test respectively, and mean gain score is 4.38 while the mean achievement scores of female students taught Electricity concepts using PhET is 9.69 and 13.61 for the pre-test and post-test respectively and mean gain score is 3.92. This implies that male students achieved slightly higher than the female students.

Test of Hypotheses

H₀₁ There is no significant difference between the mean Motivation scores of students taught Electricity concepts in physics using PhET Simulations and those taught using conventional teaching method.

Table 5: Summary of Mann Whitney U Test Results of Motivation Scores of Students in Experimental and Control Group

Groups	N	Mean Rank	Sum of Ranks	Mann Whitney U	Z	Sig.	Remark
Experimental	35	23.38	276.00				
Control	35	16.75	195.00	93.000	-2.725	.000	Sig.

Table 5 reveals Mann-Whitney U test of motivation scores of students taught Electricity concepts using PhET Simulations and those taught using conventional teaching method. The results indicate a statistically significant difference between the motivation scores of students in experimental and control groups ($z = -2.725$; $p < .05$). This implies that the null hypothesis one is not accepted.

H₀₂ There is no significant difference between the mean Achievement scores of students taught Electricity concepts in physics using PhET Simulations and those taught using conventional teaching method.

Table 6: Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) of Respondents' Scores in Achievement Test (Method*Gender)

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Partial Eta Squared
Corrected Model	124.581 ^a	4	31.145	18.501	.000	.747
Intercept	87.589	1	87.589	52.030	.000	.675
PRET	22.392	1	22.392	13.301	.001	.347
	45.275	1	45.275	26.894	.000	.518
GENDER	2.706	1	2.706	1.608	.216	.060
GENDER	.061	1	.061	.036	.850	.001
Error	42.086	65	1.683			
Total	3580.000	70				
Corrected Total	166.667	69				

a. R Squared = .747 (Adjusted R Squared = .707)

b. Computed using alpha = .05

Results in Table 6 shows there is a significant difference in treatments (PhET and Conventional Teaching methods) on students' achievement in Electricity concepts ($F_{(1,25)} = 26.894$; $p < 0.05$). Hence, null hypothesis two is not accepted. To determine the mean achievement difference between the two groups, table 6 shows a difference of $\bar{x}=5.14$ in favour of the experimental group. This implies that there is significant difference in the mean achievement scores of students taught Electricity concepts with PhET Simulations and those taught using Conventional Teaching Method.

H₀₃ There is no significant difference between the mean Motivation scores of male and female students taught Electricity concepts in physics using PhET Simulations and those taught using conventional teaching method.

Table 7: Summary of Mann Whitney U Test Results of Motivation Scores of Male and Female Students in Experimental Group

Groups	N	Mean Rank	Sum of Ranks	Mann Whitney U	Z	Sig.	Remark
Male	28	17.96	196.00				
Female	7	17.82	195.00	68.500	-1.287	.247	Not Sig.

Table 7 shows the results of the Mann Whitney U test of motivation scores of male and female students in experimental group. The results yielded no statistically significant difference in the mean motivation scores of male and female students ($z = -1.287$, $p > .05$). Therefore, the null hypothesis three is accepted.

H₀₄ There is no significant difference between the mean Achievement scores of male and female students taught Electricity concepts in physics using PhET Simulations and those taught using conventional teaching method.

Result in table 6 shows no significant difference between the mean achievement scores of male and female students taught Physics (Electricity concepts) using PhET Simulations ($F_{(1,120)} = .036$; $p = .850$). Therefore, null hypotheses four is accepted.

4. DISCUSSION

There was a significant difference between the mean motivation scores of students in the experimental and control group, with the experimental group showing higher motivation. This result also suggests that the intervention or treatment applied to the experimental group had an effect on motivation scores. The result is in line with the findings of Damola, Solomon and Friday (2024), where it was discovered that PhET had a substantial effect on the motivation of Basic Science and Technology students. The result is also supported by the findings of Prima et. al., (2018), where students who learned about the solar system with simulation as a teaching tool improved on conceptual knowledge

and motivation more than students who learned about the same thing without simulation. The study further revealed a moderate correlation between students' conceptual understanding and motivation towards learning solar system concepts. Another study which backed the findings is that of Manao et al., (2020). The study found that PhET interactive simulation combined with experiments significantly increased students' motivation. The study further revealed that PhET interactive simulations created an enjoyable and conducive learning environment which accounted for the increased students' motivation. Furthermore, Susilawati et al., (2022), study revealed that there was a significant gain in students' problem-solving skills and motivation with the use of the PhET interactive simulation as a teaching and learning resource. All these suggests that the use of the interactive PhET in teaching physics (Electricity) concepts significantly improves students' motivation.

The result also showed that the experimental group taught Electricity concepts in physics using PhET Simulations had higher achievement scores than those taught with conventional teaching method. The findings indicate that there was a significant difference between the two teaching methods on students' achievement in Electricity concepts. This is in line with Uğur, Abdillahi and Kutalmış (2017), whose findings revealed that interactive simulations integrated 5E teaching model caused significantly better acquisition of scientific concepts related to content taught and relatively higher positive attitudes towards physics than traditionally based instruction.

The findings indicate that there was no significant difference between the mean motivation scores of male and female students taught Electricity concepts in physics using PhET Simulations. This is supported by Patrick, Moses, Philip, Thomas, Abel and Isaac (2023), who found that the mean scores of students on all the motivation scales increased significantly after using the PhET simulation to teach. This is also supported by Kaluba and Christopher (2024), whose study revealed that even if boys performed statistically significantly better than girls in the experimental group, the girls from the experimental group performed statistically significantly better than the girls from the control group which showed that simulations are equally gender friendly. Therefore, we can conclude that gender does not have a significant effect on students' motivation levels in this context.

The findings indicate that there was no significant difference in the mean achievement scores between male and female students who were taught Electricity concepts using PhET simulations. Which is contrary to the findings of Pember and Achor (2017), whose findings revealed that there was a significant difference in the mean Practical Physics achievement. On the basis of gender there were no significant differences both for the two groups in practical achievement.

CONCLUSION

The findings of this study underscore the effectiveness of the PhET Simulations over the conventional method of teaching towards improving students' motivation and achievement in Electricity concepts. PhET Simulations proved to augment students' motivation and achievement further confirming its potential as a transformative instructional strategy. It was also concluded that gender does not have a significant effect on students' motivation and achievement in learning Electricity concepts. Hence, it is highly recommended for instruction at the Tertiary level and at other levels of Education. This highlights the importance of innovative teaching Strategies in improving Physics education outcomes among Colleges of Education students in Nigeria.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The following recommendations were made based on the findings:

1. Physics lecturers should make regular use of PhET simulations when teaching Electricity concepts, as the tool has been shown to boost students' motivation and achievement.
2. Colleges of Education should organize capacity-building workshops to help lecturers learn how to apply PhET simulations effectively in classroom instruction.
3. Since PhET simulations benefit both male and female students equally, lecturers should ensure that all learners have the same opportunities to engage with the simulations.

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